

Some Fuel Quality Assessment of Prepared Biodiesel from *Annona squamosa* Oil Methyl Ester

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Abstract

Nowadays, fossil fuels have been increased in prices and depletion, creates very necessary to find out an alternative fuel (biodiesel) from non-edible oil seeds. This paper deals with the transesterification of custard apple seed oil by means of methanol in presence of Potassium hydroxide catalyst at less than 60°C. The viscosity of biodiesel produced from custard apple seed oil is nearer to that of the commercially available diesel. The important properties of biodiesel such as color, specific gravity, kinematic viscosity flash point, pour point, copper strip corrosion and cetane index were found out and compared with that of *Jatropha* oil methyl ester (Biodiesel), ASTM-biodiesel standards and commercially available diesel. The study encourages the production of biodiesel from Custard Apple seed (*Annona squamosa*) oil.

Keywords: *Annona squamosa*, Transesterification, Biodiesel

Introduction

Today, more and more countries are prospering through economic reforms and becoming industrially advanced. Every sector of the economy, including the agriculture, industry, transport, commercial and domestic sectors require energy. Energy is needed approximately 47.25 % of population, and energy consumption will definitely increase further. Main stream forms of renewable energy include wind power, hydropower, solar energy, biomass, and biofuels. Energy is key factor for the sustainable development and need of energy in farms, industries and transport is substantially increased and extensive use is factor of global warming. Fossil fuels play a dominant role in the energy situation, and non-renewable, scares and extensive use lead to environmental pollution. The biofuel is being produced from different feed stock such as vegetable oil, animal fat and oil seeds. Biodiesel can be made from many oils and fats such as rape seed, palm oil, sunflower, soy, canola, tallow mustard or even from used vegetable oils and animal fats. All these feed stocks are non-toxic, biodegradable and renewable resources. Biodiesel production begins with pressing the plant seeds which yields an oil fraction to be later converted to biodiesel and a by-product so called oil cake which can be used as cattle feed. Raw oil needs filtering and esterification large-branched molecular structure in to smaller molecules similar to the fossil fuel based fuels. Fats and raw oils can chemically react with alcohol (usually methanol) during esterification process in order to get methyl ester and glycerine another by-product used in the pharmaceutical and cosmetics industries (Knothe, G. and K.R. Steidley, 2005).

Botanical Description and Oil Constituents of *Annona squamosa* L.

Annona squamosa L. is a small, well-branched [tree](#) or [shrub](#) from the family [Annonaceae](#) that bears edible fruits called [sugar-apples](#). *Annona squamosa* L. is an important fruit crop is widely distributed in Myanmar, West Indies and native of the tropical Americas. The sugar apple has been widely planted in home gardens of South Florida because of its high quality fruit and good adaptation to the area. Some fruit is found in local markets but commercial production is on a very limited scale. The common name of the *Annona squamosa* L. is sugar apple and also been known as sweetsop (English). The color of the fruit is pale green to blue-green with a deep pink bluish in some varieties. The flesh is light fragrant and sweet, creamy white to light yellow. The custard apple seeds which appears in brown to black

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color and are hard and shiny. When the extraction of oil from sweetsop seeds, 1000 g of seeds contained 260 mL of oil. The percentage of oil content obtained is 26%. Extracted seed oil was also used as a biodiesel and it can be supplied as energy in farm, industries and transport. So, renewable energy from the feedstocks of raw materials should be used and saving the maintenance of environmental pollution from non-renewable sources (Yathish, K.V, 2013).

Chemical Composition of *Annona squamosa* L. Seed

Annona squamosa seed contain major minerals such as potassium, phosphate, calcium, sulphur, iron, manganese, zinc, copper and osmium. The seeds of *Annona squamosa* contain annotemoyin-1, annotemoyin-2, squamosin and cholesteryl glucopyranoside (Yathish, K.V, 2013). The second largest constituent of *Annona squamosa* seed is the oil which contains about 26% of the seed (Siddalingappa R. H., 2015).

Material and Methods

Sample Collection and Extraction of oil

The samples of *Annona squamosa* L. seeds were collected from Paukkaung Township, Bago Region. The oil content of *A. squamosa* seeds were extracted with petroleum ether by two methods using Soxhlet and mechanical expeller. The extracted oil was prepared as a fatty acid methyl ester (biodiesel) by transesterification process using methanol and potassium hydroxide as a catalyst (Aye Aye Cho, 2015). The analysis of fatty acid methyl ester (biodiesel) compositions were characterized by FT IR (PerkinElmer C93927 Spectrum Two) and Gas Chromatography (Trace 1300 ISQ QD GC-MS) spectrometer at West Yangon University.

Determination of Fuel Quality of Prepared Biodiesel

Some fuel qualities of prepared biodiesel such as color, specific gravity, kinematic viscosity, flash point, pour point, copper strip corrosion and cetane index were determined at Thanlyin Oil Refinery Department, Ministry of Electricity and Energy, Yangon Myanmar.

Results and Discussion

Characterization of *Annona squamosa* Fatty Acid Methyl Ester (ASFAME)

The *Annona squamosa* fatty acid methyl ester was characterized by FT IR and GC-MS. From the analysis of FT IR spectrum [Fig. 1(a)], the band at 1741 cm^{-1} indicated -C=O absorption band of saturated ester and the peak at 1194 and 1168 cm^{-1} shows C-C-O stretching vibration of saturated ester linkage. Fatty acid methyl ester composition of the oil sample was analyzed by Trace 1300 ISQ QD GC-MS. Gas chromatography analysis, [Fig. 1(b)] indicates the FAME obtained from *Annona squamosa* seed oil is free of soap and the triglycerides are mostly converted to the methyl esters. The most abundant relative percentage of fatty acid methyl esters showed that it is primarily composed of palmitic acid, oleic acid and stearic acid.

Figure (1). FT IR and Gas Chromatography spectrum of *Annona squamosa* fatty acid methyl ester (ASFAME)

Table (1) Fatty acid methyl ester (FAME) composition of *Annona squamosa* L. seed oil analyzed by Gas Chromatography

R_t (min)	Identification
12.25	Hexadecanoic acid methyl ester
13.59	9-octadecenoic acid methyl ester
13.70	Octadecanoic acid methyl ester

Fuel Quality Assessment of Prepared *Annona squamosa* Fatty Acid Methyl Ester

The quality assessment of were done on fuel properties such as color, specific gravity, kinematic viscosity, flash point, pour point, copper strip corrosion and cetane index. These fuel properties were compared with ASTM standard of biodiesel and Jatropha oil methyl ester (biodiesel). The color of ASFAME was golden yellow and was nearly found to be consistent with standard biodiesel and Jatropha oil methyl ester. The specific gravity of biodiesel varies with its fatty acid composition and a denser biodiesel has higher energy content and will give better mileage and increased power. The specific gravity of ASFAME and JOME were listed to be 0.89 and 0.87 at 60 °F which are close to that of standard value of biodiesel and commercial diesel. The viscosity is important in determining optimum handling storage, and operational conditions. Fuel must have suitable flow characteristics to ensure that an adequate supply reaches injectors at different operating temperatures. The kinematic viscosity of ASFAME was found to be 4.94 cSt whereas JOME was 5.15 cSt. These values were nearly agreed with the standard range of biodiesel and higher than that of commercial diesel. The lowest temperature at which the vapour of a combustible liquid can be made to ignite momentarily in air is identified as the flash point and correlates to ignitibility of fuel. Low flash point can indicate residual methanol remaining from the conversion process. The flash point of ASFAME was found to be 97 °C and which is lower than the limit of biodiesel specification (100-170 °C). The flash point of ASFAME is higher than the JOME and commercial diesel. The pour point is the lowest temperature at which fuel samples will not flow. Therefore, the pour point provides an index of the lowest temperature of the fuel's utility for certain applications. The pour point of ASFAME and JOME were found to be (+ 12 and +3). The value of ASFAME is little higher than with standard biodiesel and commercial diesel fuel range. The copper corrosion test (ASTM D 130) refers to a measure of possible corrosion of copper, cake brass or bronze parts within the fuel system. The copper strip corrosion test is

designed to access the relative degree of corrosivity of petroleum products. The copper strip corrosion of ASFAME and JOME were found to be (1a and 2b) that less than allowed standard range (3 max) for both biodiesel. But suitable used as commercial diesel for fuel system components made of copper alloy. Cetane index is indicative of its ignition characteristics or measure of ignition quality of fuel oil. The cetane index for diesel engines is analogous to the octane rating in spark ignition engine, it is measure how easily the fuel will ignite in the engine and the smoothness of combustion. The cetane index for ASFAME was tasted to be (48.5 min). The cetane index of ASFAME was found to be in the range of standard biodiesel (48-65 min) and it was lower than the commercial diesel.

Table (2) Fuel properties of using KOH Catalysts transesterification processes of *Annona squamosa* Fatty Acid Methyl Ester (Biodiesel)

Fuel Properties	ASTM limits (BD)	ASFAME (BD)	JOME (BD)	Commercial Diesel
Color		2	2	2
Specific gravity	0.86-0.9	0.89	0.87	0.84
Kinematic viscosity (40°C) (cSt)	1.9-6.0	4.94	5.15	3.40
Flash point (°C)	100-170	97	92	70
Pour point	-15 to 10	+12	+3	-3
Copper strip corrosion (3h at 50°C)	No. 3 max	1(a)	2b	1a
Cetane index	48.0-65.0	48.5	48.72	54.50

ASFAME = *Annona squamosa* Fatty Acid Methyl Ester

JOME = Jatropha Oil Methyl Ester (Aung Kyaw Swar, 2010).

Conclusion

In this research work, *Annona squamosa* fatty acid methyl ester was carried out from *Annona squamosa* seed oil by transesterification process. The esterified sample was confirmed by FT IR and GC-MS. According to the FT IR analysis, the band at 1741 cm^{-1} indicated -C=O absorption band of saturated ester show carbonyl group for ester and their components such as sp^3 hydrocarbon, -C-C-O stretching vibration and -C-H out of plane bending. In accordance with the individual GC-MS peak indicates that the most abundant fatty acid such as palmitic acid, oleic acid and stearic acid were esterified by the transesterification process. In addition, the fuel qualities such as color, specific gravity, kinematic viscosity, flash point, pour point, copper strip corrosion and cetane index were determined. According to the fuel quality assessment, color (1a), specific gravity (0.877), kinematic viscosity (4.94 cSt), flash point (97

°C), pour point (+12), copper strip corrosion (1a) and cetane index (48.5 min) were found to be in *Annona squamosa* fatty acid methyl ester. The fuel properties of resultant biodiesel was found to consistent with ASTM D 6751 specification of biodiesel and commercial diesel. *A. squamosa* oil biodiesel can be reliable to be used as diesel substitute for diesel engines without further modification of engine pumping system. It may be inferred that *Annona squamosa* oil can be used as well as to produce quality biodiesel. Hence, the cultivation of *A. squamosa* plant can be affected as potential alternative for renewable energy sources.

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